

SROC III

Third Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

**November, 2-3rd 2024,
Ethno Complex Vrdnicka kula, Vrdnik**

SBRT region of the abdomen

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Introduction: In order to prevent early and late complications after irradiation of the region of the abdomen, new techniques and immobilization tools have been introduced that allow the patient has no unwanted side effects during and after therapy.

Goal: Prevention or mitigation of early and late complications during and after radiation

Methodology: Application of modern methods such as SBRT technique with application respiratory gating and accompanying immobilization.

Result: The quality of life of patients after completed radiotherapy is high level.

Conclusion: These modern techniques provide the patient with the possibility of a quality life during and after radiotherapy.

Keywords: SBRT, Radiologic Technologist, Radiotherapy, respiratory gating

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